

1 **Gpr147 and Adgrg1 in the trophoectoderm.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here enrichment of
9 Gpr147 and Adgrg1 in the trophoectoderm suggesting they mark the location and development transition
10 of the embryo during TE commitment in stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

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